

Brucellosis in Livestock animals

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Abstract

Brucellosis is contagious disease caused by ingestion of unpasteurized milk or undercooked meat of infected animals, or close contact with infected animals' secretions. It is also known as undulant fever, Malta fever, and Mediterranean fever. Four species infect humans: *B. abortus*, *B. canis*, *B. melitensis*, and *B. suis*. *B. melitensis* is primarily cause disease in cattle. *B. canis* affects dogs. *B. melitensis* is the most virulent species. it usually infects goats and occasionally sheep. *B. suis* mostly infects pigs. Symptoms include profuse sweating and joint and muscle pain. Brucellosis has been recognized in animals and humans since may years.

Introduction

Etiology:

Brucella species are small, gram negative, non-motile, non-spore forming, rod-shaped coco bacilli bacteria.

Reservoir host:

Reservoirs host include sheep, cattle, swine, and goats. Bison and deer may also harbor Brucella spp.

Mode of transmission:

Transmission by direct contact with infected animals or tissues including: blood, urine, vaginal discharges, aborted fetuses, and placentas. It may also be transmitted through consumption of unpasteurized milk or dairy products from infected animals. Airborne transmission may occur by inhalation of aerosols in laboratory. Human-to-human transmission is rare, but congenital brucellosis has been reported, and infected mothers may transmit to infants through breastfeeding.

Action of physical and chemical agent:

Killed by heating them to 60 °C for 10 minutes, Susceptible to acidic pH, disinfectants and sunlight. Survive for a long time in fetus. Remain for a long time in cold temperature.

Clinical sign of brucellosis in animals:

Cattle and Goat: Abortion (7th-9th month-cattle and 3rd or 4th month-sheep), Hygroma of knee, Abortion is associated with retained placenta. Also cause stillborn or weak calves and reduced milk yield. Seminal vesicle, ampullae, testicles and epidymides are infected in bulls. Testicular abscesses. Long-standing infections may result in arthritic joints.

Sheep: Abortion, lameness, mastitis, diarrhea, Deterioration of semen quality, Epididymal enlargement Spermatocetes contain spermatic fluid. Tunics become thickened and fibrous. Testes show fibrous atrophy.

Horse: Chronic inflammatory condition referred as fistulous withers, poll evil and joint infections. Fistulous withers occurring in supraspinous bursa. Poll evil occurring in supra-atlantal bursa.

Pigs: Abortion, lameness, paralysis, infertility

Dogs: Abortion, early embryonic death, dermatitis of scrotum, testicular atrophy

Clinical sign of brucellosis in human:

- Fever
- weakness
- malaise
- anorexia
- headache
- pain in muscles and joint and back

Some symptoms may persist for longer period- Recurrent fever, arthritis, swelling of the testicle and scrotal area, Endocarditis, chronic fatigue, depression, swelling of the liver or spleen.

Public health significance:

According to WHO laboratory biosafety manual, brucellosis is classifying in Risk group III.

Brucellosis is readily transmissible to humans causing acute febrile illness (undulant fever)

In chronic infection, serious complication affecting the musculo-skeletal, cardiovascular and central nervous system

Risk to veterinarians and farmers who handle infected animals and aborted fetuses or placenta.

Diagnosis:

- Rose Bengal Test
- Standard Tube Agglutination Test
- ELISA
- PCR
- Bacteriological isolation of organism

Treatment:

Antibiotics are used for treat the infection and prevention of disease. Longer courses of therapy may be needed if there are complications.

Prevention and control:

Vaccination of calves with live *Brucella abortus* strain 19 at an age of 3-6 months offer high level immunity. One dose gives immunity up to fifth pregnancy.

Proper disposal of aborted fetuses.

Pasteurization of milk and milk products.

Periodical testing of herd.

Prevention of human brucellosis is dependent on control of the disease in livestock.

Lack of human vaccines and effective control measure make it necessary for the veterinarian and other health care workers to take protective measures.

References:

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